

Report “Creation of a polymeric material profile for FEA analysis starting from the results of experimental laboratory tests”

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Compared to the first phase of the study, which began with FEA analysis of a 316L steel samples to verify the accuracy of the simulation through experimental laboratory tests, the approach for polymeric materials was entirely opposite because the Ntopology software does not include specific libraries for this type of material.

Therefore in the first phase of the study, the goal was to verify the accuracy of FEA simulations by conducting laboratory tests on samples. In this second phase, the objective is to start from the laboratory test results to create a profile usable in FEA analysis.

The 3D printing technology used was FDM (Fused Deposition Modeling), which allows for the production of anisotropic components only. However, the orientation of the sample on the print bed was not considered. The dog bone-shaped sample was always positioned parallel to the print bed, as illustrated in the figure below.

Based on scientific literature, some of the most significant parameters influencing the mechanical strength of the components were identified,

This study will focus on the following only:

- Layer thickness
- Printing temperature
- Infill density
- Infill patterns

STEP 1: analysis of the scientific literature

Many researchers have attempted to optimize the parameters related to fused deposition modelling production to print high-quality parts.

Anitha et al. studied the potential influence on surface roughness based on various set parameters. The results highlighted that to achieve optimal surface roughness properties, the best possible values for layer height, line width, and deposition speed were 0.3556 mm, 0.537 mm, and 200 mm/s, respectively.

Bene et al. investigated the effects of production parameters (including print orientation, layer thickness, and infill density) on the mechanical properties.

Nunez et al. studied dimensional accuracy, flatness, and surface texture. They found that layer thickness and infill density influenced surface finish and dimensional accuracy. The results showed that low layer thicknesses and high infill densities resulted in better surface finish, while high layer thicknesses and high infill densities improved the dimensional accuracy.

Kaveh et al. sought to optimize printing parameters for parts fabricated with ABS, PLA, and HIPS materials. The results showed that parameters such as nozzle temperature, feed rate, flow rate and line width affected the quality of the printed samples.

Baich et al. investigated the effects of infill pattern and printing time on the mechanical performance of ABS-printed parts. Mechanical properties deteriorated as infill density decreased.

Harpool studied the strength of PLA parts with four different infill patterns: rectilinear, diamond, honeycomb, and solid. Samples printed with a 15% infill density showed that the honeycomb pattern provided the maximum strength, demonstrating that infill geometry significantly affects the mechanical properties of printed parts.

Alafaghani et al. experimentally studied the influence of process parameters on the mechanical properties of printed parts under various working conditions: infill pattern, print speed, infill percentage, build direction, layer thickness, and nozzle temperature. They found that infill pattern, infill density and print speed had only slight effects on tensile properties.

More recently, Cristian and Dudescu observed the effects of raster angle (0, 30, 45, and 90 degrees), infill density (20–100%), and infill patterns (triangular, grid, rectilinear, full honeycomb, fast honeycomb, and oscillating) in 3D printing. Their experimental results showed an increase in Young's modulus with a higher infill density percentage. Additionally, raster angles of 0 and 90 degrees provided the best strength.

The work of Cristian et al. reported slightly different Young's modulus values for six different infill patterns. Furthermore, build direction, layer thickness, and nozzle temperature were

shown to significantly influence mechanical properties, such as tensile strength, Young's modulus, and stiffness.

Rahman et al. studied six factors that can influence FDM-printed parts. The experimental results showed that the most appropriate values for bed temperature, nozzle temperature, print speed, infill density, layer thickness, and number of cycles were 110°C, 220°C, 55 mm/s, 15%, 0.2 mm, and 1, respectively.

Additionally, Panda et al.'s work indicated that variations in wall thickness and cell size of a honeycomb pattern could significantly affect the mechanical properties of printed parts.

Goyanes et al. argued that nozzle travel speed and print speed in a 3D printing process could affect the quality of printed parts. They recommended using a travel speed of 150 mm/s for economical printing. For very high quality, a travel speed of 100 mm/s could be used. However, at very high travel speeds, such as 200 mm/s, parts might lose some steps in molten polymer deposition. Print speed refers to the rate at which the molten polymer is extruded and deposited. Any increase in print speed would require a corresponding increase in nozzle temperature to achieve complete filament melting before deposition.

Behzadnasab and Yousefi explored the possible effects of nozzle temperature (180°C, 200°C, 220°C, and 240°C) on the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts. They found that the strength of a 3D-printed PLA part increased as nozzle temperature rose to 240°C. However, a nozzle temperature above 240°C caused polymer degradation, which represents the typical upper limit for nozzle temperature in 3D printing of polymeric materials. Moreover, print speed can significantly influence the mechanical properties of printed parts. Setting a high print speed may result in poor bonding between layers, potentially leading to decreased mechanical strength. In general, print speed significantly affects the cooling rate and melting rate of the material, which could cause poor interlayer bonding.

Step 2: Samples preparation

Dog bone-shaped specimen modelling

Dog-bone shaped specimen is used to determine the elastic and strength properties by both compression and tension testing.

3D Printer

For producing the samples Crealty CR M-4 3D printer has been used. Crealty CR M-4.

Material

PLA black BASF Ultrafuse 1,75mm

Slicer and main parameters

Slicing software to create the g-code to start the manufacturing: Ultimaker CURA 5.4.0

Nozzle: 0,4 mm

Layer height: variable

Walls: 3 (1,2mm)

Top/Bottom: 6 (1,2mm)

Printing temperature: variable

Initial printing temperature: 195° C

Bed temperature: 55° C

Print speed: 100 mm/s

Wall speed: 50 mm/s

Top/bottom speed: 50 mm/s

Initial layer speed: 20 mm/s

Final layer speed: 20 mm/s

Travel speed: 250 mm/s

Retraction: 6,5 mm

Retraction speed: 25 mm/s

Infill density: variable

Infill pattern: variable

Area of investigation

Effect of infill density on tensile properties

The infill density can affect the strength of 3D printed parts.

The tensile modulus can be increased by increasing the infill density.

Although 100% infill density can provide the highest strength, it can affect the overall cost negatively by increasing the printing time and the amount of material consumed.

For some 3D printed parts, there is no need of using 100% infill density given the nature of the application. Hence, the determination of the required infill density based on the nature and application of the product would be quite important for mass scale production lines to optimize the resources.

For this study, a total of 12 samples were printed, keeping all parameters constant with the exception of the infill density:

- Layer height: 0,2mm
- Printing temperature: 205°C
- Infill density: 25%, 50%, 100%
- Infill pattern: grid

Effect of infill patterns on tensile properties

To investigate which infill patterns guarantees better mechanical performance were used five different types (linear, octet, zigzag, triangles and grid).

In this case, a total of 20 samples were printed, keeping all parameters constant with the exception of the infill patterns:

- Layer height: 0,2mm
- Printing temperature: 210°C
- Infill density:: 50%
- Infill pattern: linear, octet, zigzag, triangles grid

Effect of the printing temperature on the tensile properties

On the basis of the scientific study the printing temperature has a significant effect on the tensile modulus and only a slight effect on the mass of the printed parts.

To evaluate the effects of the set nozzle temperature on the mechanical properties of 3D printed parts, PLA samples were printed at three different set nozzle temperatures: 205 C, 215 C, 230 C. (12 samples printed).

- Layer height: 0,2mm
- Printing temperature: 205°C -215°- C230°C
- Infill density:: 30%
- Infill pattern: grid

Effect of layer thickness on tensile properties

The purpose of this study was to optimize the mechanical properties through modulation of the printing layer thickness.

Specimens were tested with three different layer thickness: 0,12 mm, 0,20mm 0,28mm with initial layer 0,2mm (12 samples printed).

- Layer height: 0,12mm – 0,20mm - 0.28mm
- Printing temperature: 215°C
- Infill density:: 50%
- Infill pattern: triangles

Next STEP: experimental laboratory tests and creation of a FEA profile for NTopology

All the samples printed has been sent to University of Udine for experimental tests.

The results will be appropriately processed for properly setting the parameters to use in NTopology's FEA analysis.